

EFFECT OF MARKETING STRATEGY ON BANK PERFORMANCE: EVIDENCE FROM BERHAN INTERNATIONAL BANK SHARE COMPANEY, ADDIS ABABA BRANCHES

Mesfin Yayna Ganta*

Ph.D. Scholar- Parul University, Waghodia, Vadodara Gujarat, India

Dr. Kunjal Sinha

Director, Centre for Continuing Education and Online Learning - Parul University,
Waghodia, Vadodara Gujarat, India

*Corresponding author : Mesfin Yayna Ganta

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of Marketing Strategies on bank performance in the case of Berhan International Bank Share Company, Addis Ababa Branch. Explanatory research design along with a quantitative research approach was employed to conduct the study. The data were collected using questionnaire. The collected data were analyzed using correlation and multiple linear regression with the help of SPSS software version 26. The findings revealed that product, price, promotion, and location all had an impact on the performance of the Berhan International Bank of Addis Ababa branch. Delivering quality services, using technology correctly, applying product differentiation methods correctly, diversifying the product, and delivering a product that meets the needs of customers all have a significant impact on bank performance. Similarly, the availability of reasonable service charges, higher interest rates on savings deposits, interest-earning in a relatively short period, low-interest rates on loans, and free book opening have a significant impact on bank performance. Similarly, promoting a product or service to attract potential customers, using appropriate promotional tools, properly publishing a product or service for customers, and having a budget available to use appropriate promotional tools all have a significant impact on bank performance. The location of the bank has an impact on its profitability. Bank branches located close to home/work, in a convenient location, with convenient opening and closing hours, and having many branches in different locations all have a significant impact on bank performance. Based on the major findings, it was recommended to provide quality services, diversify bank products, open a branch in a convenient location, and promote the bank.

Key words: Placing, Price, Product, Promotion, Bank Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Marketing Strategies can be defined as the primary goal of increasing sales and gaining a sustainable competitive advantage. Marketing Strategies encompasses all fundamental, short-term, and long-term marketing activities concerned with the analysis of a company's strategic initial situation and the formulation, evaluation, and selection of market-oriented

strategies, thereby contributing to the company's goals and marketing objectives (Tseng, 2007). Bank Marketing Strategies imply an examination of the market and its surroundings, customer purchasing habits, competitive activities, and the needs and capabilities of marketing intermediaries (Weifels, 2002). Ethiopia's banking industry is challenged by fluctuating demand and fierce competition. The banking industry's competitive environment is widely recognized as complex, dynamic, and highly segmented, making customer acquisition difficult (Silva, 2006).

Companies are seeing internationalization of their activities as a way to stay competitive in today's globalization market. Marketing strategies have become an important tool globally for any organization to remain competitive and stronger in a market environment. Strategy, according to Aremu and Lawal (2012), is a pattern of resource allocation decisions made throughout an organization. This includes both desired goals and beliefs about what methods are acceptable and, more importantly, unacceptable for achieving them. With the growing importance of the financial sector, pressures for more effective financial marketing management are increasing. Frontline sales performance is dependent on effective marketing strategies.

Marketing strategy research has primarily concentrated on one of two areas: marketing strategy formulation or marketing strategy implementation. Marketing strategy formulation research investigates the effect of various variables on the development of marketing strategies themselves (Weifels, 2002). As bank customers had the opportunity to select from a variety of offers from various banks and other financial institutions, they became more selective, compelling bankers to enthusiastically project their presence. This resulted in fierce competition in the sector.

Marketing strategies have evolved as an alternative means for businesses to establish strong, long-term relationships with their customers. As part of Marketing Strategies, it seeks to acquire and retain customers by providing high-quality customer service, and has thus become one of the keys to achieving strong competitiveness in today's markets. Marketing Strategies has received a lot of attention in both academic research and practice, despite the fact that the last decade has seen some significant changes and dominance of Marketing

Strategies in the business field (Egan, 2001). Market buyers and sellers achieve mutual benefits through developing effects, even though switching behaviors occur at various stages of a partnership. Marketing Strategies tactics are thus methods for putting Marketing Strategies into action (Tseng, 2007).

Banks can increase their profits by shifting their focus from short-term objectives to long-term marketing strategies. Researchers in Ethiopia, such as Azmeraw (2013) and Abesolom (2013), conducted studies on assessing the practice of marketing strategies in two different organizations and discovered a lack of marketing strategy implementation. The researchers also demonstrated that Marketing Strategy tactics have a positive effect on behavioral loyalty, which affects customer retention. Marketers must look beyond traditional marketing strategies to gain a competitive advantage in such a crowded marketplace (Dehghan et al., 2015).

Due to intense competition, Ethiopian banks have attempted to devise new strategies in order to improve their performance. Over the last few years, the Ethiopian banking sector has seen significant growth. The industry continues to provide significant profit opportunities for the major players, but marketing strategies are underutilized (Abulkadir and Yasin, 2019). There have been studies on the importance of marketing strategies in improving sales in organizations, but there has been little research on the effects of marketing strategies on performance among Ethiopian banks. This is the primary reason for the researcher's decision to investigate this topic. As a result, the purpose of this study was to investigate the impact of marketing strategies on bank performance in the case of Berhan International Bank Addis Ababa Branch. The study also have the following specific objectives:

1. To examine the effect of product strategy on bank performance.
2. To evaluate the effect of promotion strategy on bank performance.
3. To examine the effect of price strategy on bank performance.
4. To investigate the effect of placing strategy on bank performance.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study investigates the impact of four key marketing strategies (product strategies, promotion strategies, price strategies, and placing strategies) on bank performance. Product Strategies encompass the development and management of banking products and services tailored to meet customer needs and preferences, aiming to enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty. Promotion Strategies involve the various methods and channels used to communicate and market these products to potential and existing customers, driving awareness and engagement. Price Strategies focus on the pricing models and competitive pricing structures implemented to attract and retain customers while ensuring profitability. Placing Strategies, or distribution strategies, address the accessibility and convenience of banking services through various channels, including physical branches and digital platforms. Collectively, these independent variables are hypothesized to significantly influence the dependent variable, Bank Performance.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study's research design was explanatory. Because explanatory research design is best when the goal of the research is to identify factors associated with the dependent variable or to understand the best predictors of the dependent variable (Oleary, 2004). In addition, the researcher used a quantitative research approach. This method refers to the type of

information derived from quantitative data, such as numerical scores, metrics, and so on. The quantitative approach aids in quantitatively quantifying or objectively measuring specific variables, making descriptive analysis simple and manageable. As a result, throughout the study, the researcher used a quantitative research approach to compute and interpret numerical data.

The researcher employed quantitative data collection methods. The study used both primary and secondary data sources to present a diverse range of information. Primary data were gathered from bank employees and bank managers via a survey questionnaire. Secondary data were gathered from previous research reviews, journals, articles, and internet web sites. In terms of data types, the researcher gathered quantitative data from bank employees.

The study population included all Berhan International Bank employees working in all Addis Ababa branches at the time of the study. Berhan International Bank employs 125 people across all of its branches. As a result, in terms of sample size, all branch managers and all employees were used as a census. This is due to the fact that the number of employees employed in all Berhan International Bank Addis Ababa branches is manageable.

As previously stated, the researcher collected primary data from selected target groups via questionnaire. The questionnaire included both open-ended and closed-ended questions to reflect their opinions and experiences with the bank's Marketing Strategies practices regarding products, pricing, promotion, and location-related questions.

The questionnaire data was entered into SPSS software version 26 and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. To investigate the impact of marketing strategies on bank performance, inferential statistics such as correlation and multiple linear regression analysis were used.

The study's primary goal was to investigate the impact of marketing strategies on bank performance. However, before fitting selected variables into the multiple linear regression model, the multicollinearity problem among continuous variables and the relationship between discrete variables must be tested, as this has a significant impact on parameter estimates. Multicollinearity refers to a situation in which it is difficult to identify the independent variable's separate effect on the dependent variable due to their strong relationship (Gujarati, 2003). Multicollinearity is defined as a situation in which explanatory variables are highly correlated.

As a result, the variance inflation factor (VIF) is used to test for multicollinearity in continuous variables. As R^2 approaches 1, there is collinearity of explanatory variables. The variable X_i is more upsetting or collinear when VIF is larger. The variable is said to be highly collinear if the VIF is greater than 10 (this will happen if R^2 is greater than 0.80). (Gujarati, 2003). Tolerance can also be used to test for multicollinearity in continuous variables. Tolerance is one if X_i is uncorrelated with the other explanatory variable, and zero if it is perfectly related to the other explanatory variables. A popular multicollinearity measure associated with the VIF is defined as:

$$VIF(X_j) = (1 - R_j^2)^{-1} \text{-----} (1)$$

Where R_j^2 denotes the multiple correlation coefficients between independent variables; the greater the value of R_j^2 , the greater the value of $VIF(X_j)$, resulting in higher collinearity in the variable (X_j).

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + X_1\beta_1 + X_2\beta_2 + X_3\beta_3 + X_4\beta_4 + e \text{-----} (2)$$

3. RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

In this study, the participants involved in responding the questionnaire were Berhan international bank employees. Out of 125 questionnaires distributed to respondents, 112(89.6%) were collected while 13(10.4%) of the questionnaire remained uncollected. Therefore, analysis was made based on the responses obtained from 112 questionnaires. This indicates that there were high rate of response.

3.1. The Relationship Between Variables in a Study

Correlation coefficients can have values ranging from -1 (a perfect negative relationship) to +1 (a perfect positive relationship) or a direct relationship between two variables. A value of 0 denotes that there is no linear relationship between two variables (kothari, 2004). The independent variables were analyzed one by one in this section using correlation analysis to determine their individual relationship with the dependent variable. Before conducting the regression analysis, independent variables such as product, price, promotion, and placement were tested for their degree of relationship with bank performance. To determine the strength and type of correlation between variables, use the table below as a guideline for variable discussion.

Table 1: Rule of Thumb for about the Strength of Correlation of Coefficient

Range of Coefficient	Description of Strength
$\pm.81$ to ± 1.00	Very strong
$\pm.61$ to $\pm .80$	Strong
$\pm.41$ to $\pm.60$	Moderate
$\pm.21$ to $\pm.40$	Weak
$\pm.00$ to $\pm.20$	None

Source: Bhattacharjee (2012)

Table 1 shows the correlation between bank performance and independent variables (product, price, promotion and placing) of the study.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis Result

Variables		Product	Promotion	Price	Placing	Bank Performance
Product	Correlation	1				
	Sig.					
Promotion	Correlation	.186	1			
	Sig.	.049				
Price	Correlation	.336	.269	1		
	Sig.	.000	.004			
Placing	Correlation	.394	.388	.316	1	
	Sig.	.000	.000	.001		
Bank Performance	Correlation	.517	.450	.558	.647	1
	Sig.	.000	.000	.000	.000	

Source: Model output, 2022

The correlation analysis of the relationship between product and bank performance reveals that product has a positive and statistically significant association with bank performance ($r = 0.517$, $p < 0.01$). This indicated that the product has a strong link to bank performance. Similarly, there is a positive and statistically significant relationship between promotion and bank performance ($r = 0.450$, $p < 0.01$). Similarly, there is a positive and statistically significant relationship between price and bank performance ($r = 0.558$, $p < 0.01$). Finally, there is a positive and statistically significant relationship between placement and bank performance ($r = 0.647$, $p < 0.01$). According to Bhattacharjee (2012), the result implies that all of the independent variables have a moderate to strong relationship with the dependent variable.

3.2. The Effect of Marketing Strategies on Bank Performance

The extent to which the independent (explanatory) variables explain the variance in the dependent (explained) variance was determined using multiple regression analysis. Multiple linear regression analysis is used in this study to assess the level of effect that multiple

independent variables have on a single dependent variable. In order to ensure research quality, linearity, normality, and multicollinearity tests are performed prior to using regression analysis to test the effect of marketing strategies on bank performance.

4.4.2.1. Linearity Test

Linearity refers to the degree to which the change in the dependent variable is related to the change in the independent variables. Therefore, the results of the linearity test were presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The Linearity test of Standardized Residual

Source: Model output, 2022

To determine whether the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables is linear; plots of the regression residuals through SPSS software had been used. The scatter plot of residuals shows no large difference in the spread of the residuals as can be seen from left to right on Figure 1. This result suggests that the predicted relationship is linear. Similarly, the figure shows the distribution of residuals around its mean of zero. Hence the linearity assumption is fulfilled as required based on the above figure. Therefore,

it is possible to conclude that the inferences that the researcher make about the population parameter from the sample is valid.

4.4.2.2. Normality Test

The other important diagnostic test conducted in this paper is the normality assumption. Normality test is used to determine whether a data set is modeled for normal distribution or not. The Histogram result is presented as follows;

Figure 2: Frequency Distribution of Standardized Residual

Source: Model output, 2022

The Normality test on Figure 2 shows the frequency distribution of the standardized residuals compared to a normal distribution. Although there are some residuals (e.g., those occurring around 0) that are relatively far away from the curve, many of the residuals are fairly close. Moreover, the histogram is bell shaped which lead to infer that the residual (disturbance or errors) are normally distributed. Thus, violations of the normally assumption is not a serious problem.

4.4.2.3. Multicollinearity Test

Under this section multicollinearity test were checked using variance inflation factor (VIF) and tolerance in Table 3.

Table 3: Multicollinearity assumption

Independent variables	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Product strategies	.795	1.257
Promotion strategies	.826	1.211
Price strategies	.825	1.212
Placing strategies	.726	1.377

Source: Model output, 2022

One of the information included in Table 3 is collinearity statistics, which are associated with the extent of correlation between independent variables. If there is a high correlation between two independent variables, the regression model assumes redundancy of one of these variables that the significance of it becomes too low and its coefficient also be negatively affected. The problem is checked by Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). A tolerance of $>.10$ and a VIF < 10 are considered as good enough to minimize the effect of multicollinearity (Miller & Whicker,1999). Thus, the result implies that the regression model is not affected by higher correlation between two independent variables. Based on this framework multiple regressions were done using all variables, namely the dependent and independent variables available in the dataset. The researcher paid due attention to the following model by taking bank performance as dependent variable and considering product, price, promotion and placing as independent variable.

$$\text{Bank Performance} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{Product} + \beta_2 * \text{Promotion} + \beta_3 * \text{Price} + \beta_4 * \text{Placing} + \varepsilon$$

The analysis was undertaken to identify the predictors of bank performance as conceptualized in the regression model. To get the answer for the question "to what extent the independent (predictor) variables predict the bank performance?" inferential statistical technique with regard to multiple regression was employed.

Regression identifies how much each independent variable has an effect on the dependent variable. Multiple regression analysis calculates multiple correlation coefficients (R^2); it is the portion of variance in the dependent variables explained by the independent variables. The contribution of the independent variables towards dependent variables is measured by the Beta value and can be explained on the basis of p or t-value.

Table 4: Results of Regression Analysis Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.789 ^a	.622	.608	.22425

a. Predictors: (Constant), Placing, Price, Promotion, Product

b. Dependent Variable: Bank Performance

Source: Model output, 2022

According to the model summary of multiple linear regression analysis, the R-value of the model as per Table 4 was 0.789 which shows the highest degree of relationship between independent and dependent variables. The adjusted R^2 value of the regression model was 0.608, indicating that 60.8% of variance in bank performance was accounted by product, price, promotion, and placing. The remaining 39.2% of variance in bank performance was accounted by other variables not included in this study.

Table 5: Results of ANOVA Output

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8.869	4	2.217	44.090	.000 ^b
	Residual	5.381	107	.050		
	Total	14.250	111			

- a. Dependent Variable: Bank Performance
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Placing, Price, Promotion, Product

Source: Model output, 2022

The ANOVA table (Table 5) indicated that the multiple regression model itself is statistically significant or not significant. Because R^2 is not a test of statistical significance (it only measures explained variation in Y from the predictor Xs), the f-ratio is used to test whether or not R^2 could have occurred by chance alone. In short, the f-ratio found in the ANOVA table measures the probability of chance departure from a straight line. On results of the output found in the ANOVA table, the model is statistically significant when product, price, promotion and placing were included ($F=44.09$, $p<0.001$). Therefore, the overall equation was found to be statistically significant.

Table 6: Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
1	(Constant)	.868	.211	Beta	4.110	.000
	Product	.154	.046	.226	3.387	.001
	Promotion	.099	.037	.172	2.635	.010
	Price	.224	.047	.311	4.761	.000
	Placing	.288	.051	.393	5.642	.000

Note: B= Regression coefficient (Estimate), Std.Error = Standard Error, Dependent variable = Bank Performance

Source: Model output, 2022

Based on Table 6, using “ β ”(unstandardized) coefficients, the regression equation of the research model becomes in the form indicated below. The regression equation is interpreted in the following few paragraphs. Four variables were included in the model, all predictors have found to be a significant effect on the bank performance. These are product, price, promotion and placing. Therefore, the interpretations of these variables are as follows.

$$\text{Bank Performance (Y)} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{Product} + \beta_2 * \text{Promotion} + \beta_3 * \text{Price} + \beta_4 * \text{Placing} + \varepsilon$$

$$\text{Bank Performance} = 0.868 + 0.154 * \text{Product} + 0.099 * \text{Promotion} + 0.224 * \text{Price} + 0.288 * \text{Placing} + .207$$

Product has a significant and positive impact on bank performance. The beta coefficient and p-value results indicate that the bank improves its performance by 0.154 as a result of a one-unit increase in product quality. According to the beta coefficient values, a 0.154 unit increase in bank performance is predicted for every unit increase in product quality. Kamau (2013) argued that product differentiation strategy has a positive and statistically significant effect on sales performance in light of this finding.

Promotion has a significant and positive impact on bank performance. This implies that promotion has a significant impact on CBE performance. According to the beta coefficient, a one unit increase in the availability of good promotion leads to a 0.099 unit increase in bank performance. According to Kotler (2007), promotions have become a critical factor in the product marketing mix, which consists of the specific blend of advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, public relations, and direct marketing tools that the company uses to pursue its advertising and marketing objectives.

In the study area, price was discovered to be a determinant factor for bank performance. At the 0.1% level of significance, the beta coefficient for price was found to be positive and statistically significant. The positive relationship implies that if the product price is reasonable, the bank can perform well. Furthermore, the beta coefficient values predicted that for every unit increase in pricing, a 0.224 unit increase in bank performance would be predicted. As a result, the result implied that product prices have a positive effect on bank performance. Owomoyela et al. (2013) argued that product influences have a significant impact on business performance in response to this finding.

The placement of a product determines where and how potential customers can access it. Table 6 shows that placing has positive and significant effect on bank performance. According to the regression coefficient, a one unit increase in placement leads to a 0.288

unit increase in bank performance. As a result, the null hypothesis, stating that placement has no significant effect on CBE performance, is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. In relation to this discovery, Owomoyela et al. (2013) agreed that location has a significant impact on business performance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Product has an impact on bank performance. Product refers to the physical appearance of the product, as well as its packaging and labeling. Information that can influence whether a consumer notices, examines, and purchases a product in-store. As a result, the bank should provide quality services, diversify their product offerings, and provide products that meet the needs of their customers.

The pricing strategy of a bank has a significant impact on its performance. The availability of reasonable service charges, higher interest rates on savings deposits, interest earning in a relatively short period of time, low interest rates on loans, and free book opening have a significant impact on bank performance. To retain existing customers and attract new customers, the bank should open a free book and offer low interest rates on loans. The selected banks should also offer higher interest rates on savings deposits.

Promotion has a significant impact on bank performance as well. Promotion is essential to the market exchange process because it communicates with current and potential stakeholders, as well as the general public. Every company or store must assume the role of communicator and promoter. Product/service promotion to attract potential customers, use of appropriate promotional tools, proper publication of product/service for customers, and having available budget to use appropriate promotional tools all have a significant impact on bank performance. As a result, the selected banks should use appropriate promotional tools to make the right people aware of the product's benefits. Furthermore, the selected banks should have sufficient funds to use appropriate promotional tools.

Placing strategy was discovered to be an important factor in bank performance in the study area. The bank's location has an impact on its profitability. Bank branches located close to home/work, in a convenient location, with convenient opening and closing hours, and having many branches in different locations all have a significant impact on bank performance. As a result, the chosen banks should have numerous branches in various locations and convenient opening and closing hours.

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